

SYNTHESIS AND INVESTIGATION OF THE ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF MIXED-LIGAND COORDINATION COMPOUNDS OF COBALT(II) ION WITH KETOROLAC

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Abstract. This article presents the results of research on the synthesis and analysis of mixed-ligand coordination compounds of cobalt (II) ion with ketorolac and amides. Solvent-based methods were selected for the synthesis process, in which cobalt (II) salts (such as chloride or acetate), ketorolac, and various amides (formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide) reacted in specific molar ratios to form new coordination compounds. To determine the structure and composition of the complexes, IR, UV-Vis, and NMR spectral analyses, as well as elemental analysis and X-ray diffraction (XRD), were employed. Thermal analysis was used to establish the thermal stability of the complexes. During the study, the coordination interactions of ligands with cobalt (II) ions, their electronic configuration, and biological activity were examined, and corresponding conclusions were drawn.

Keywords: ketorolac, formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide, coordination compound, synthesis, analysis, coordination capacity, thermal stability, solubility, reaction yield.

Introduction. One of the most relevant areas of modern coordination chemistry and bioinorganic chemistry is the synthesis of new coordination compounds based on biologically active ligands and the study of their properties. In particular, complexes of transition metals such as cobalt attract special interest due to their wide range of biological activities, including antibacterial, antifungal, and antitumor properties [1,2]. The cobalt (II) ion, owing to its electronic configuration and wide coordination numbers, can form stable coordination compounds with a variety of ligands; their structural features and bioactivity largely depend on the nature of the ligands [3]. Ketorolac is a systemically active non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), whose pharmacological effect is mainly achieved through the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. However, at high doses, it carries the risk of damaging the gastrointestinal mucosa [4]. In modern pharmaceutical chemistry, the synthesis of metal complexes of drugs is considered a promising approach to enhance drug efficacy and reduce side effects. It is well established that when organic ligands form complexes with metal ions, their biological activity can significantly increase, often associated with improved metabolic stability and enhanced solubility in water [5].

Ligands containing amide groups are widely used in coordination chemistry, as they possess strong coordination ability and can form stable chelate complexes with various metal ions [6]. From this perspective, combining ketorolac (which contains a carboxylic acid group) with different amide ligands to design mixed-ligand cobalt (II) complexes exhibiting synergistic effects is highly expedient. The aim of this study is to synthesize new mixed-ligand coordination compounds of cobalt (II) ion with ketorolac and various amides (such as formamide, acetamide, and nicotinamide), and to investigate their composition and structure using modern physicochemical methods (IR, XRD, atomic absorption spectroscopy, and elemental analysis).

Preliminary screening of the antioxidant and antibacterial activities of the synthesized complexes is also among the important tasks of this research.

Literature review. In recent years, coordination chemistry has been rapidly developing and has found broad applications in medicine, pharmaceuticals, biology, and materials science. Numerous scientific sources report that coordination compounds involving metal ions can interact with a wide range of bioactive molecules, significantly altering their chemical and pharmacological properties [7,8,9]. The coordination chemistry of cobalt (II) ion has been at the center of many investigations, as it can form stable complexes with various organic ligands in tetrahedral and octahedral configurations. The biological activity of cobalt complexes is attributed to their participation in redox processes and their catalytic properties resembling those of enzymatic reactions [10,11,12]. Many studies have reported the antibacterial, antifungal, and antitumor activities of cobalt complexes [13,14].

Ketorolac ($C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$) is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that inhibits prostaglandin biosynthesis. However, due to its limited solubility and stability, research has focused on enhancing its pharmacological effectiveness through the formation of coordination complexes with various metal ions [15,16]. In recent years, ketorolac complexes synthesized with Zn(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), and Co(II) have demonstrated significant antibacterial and antioxidant activity [17,18]. Amides (such as carboxamides and sulfonamides) are important ligands in coordination chemistry, as they coordinate to metal ions through nitrogen or oxygen atoms. In particular, complexes synthesized from sulfonamides have been shown to possess high biological activity [19,20]. In mixed-ligand complexes, the simultaneous presence of different ligands around the metal center increases stability, redistributes electron density, and consequently may enhance pharmacological activity [21].

Although cobalt ion complexes with various NSAIDs and amide derivatives have been studied, mixed-ligand complexes of ketorolac with amides have not been sufficiently investigated [22]. Existing research highlights that such complexes exhibit noteworthy physicochemical properties (UV-Vis, IR, PXRD, thermal analysis) as well as significant biological activity (antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant) [23,24]. This underlines the relevance of synthesizing new complexes and analyzing their structural and biological characteristics.

Research methodology. I. First, the required reagents and apparatus were collected, including $CoCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$ (ketorolac), amides (formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide), ethanol, NaOH, distilled water, and laboratory glassware. The synthesis of the complex compound with the composition $Co(ket)_2(HCONH_2)_2(H_2O)_2$ was carried out as follows.

A solution of 0.745 g (2.0 mmol) ketorolac tromethamine in 20 mL of hot methanol was prepared and transferred into a burette. In the next step, 0.238 g (1.0 mmol) of $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was dissolved in 10 mL of a methanol–water mixture. Separately, a solution of formamide ($HCONH_2$, 0.090 g, 2.0 mmol) was prepared. The cobalt salt solution was slowly added, with constant stirring, into the ketorolac solution over 15–20 minutes. The resulting green solution was then treated with the third component, formamide, which was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was heated at 50–60 °C (without boiling) for 2–3 hours using a magnetic stirrer. The mixture was subsequently cooled to room temperature, which improved the crystallization of the complex.

The pH of the reaction mixture was checked using pH paper or a pH meter. To adjust the pH to 6.5–7.0, 2–3 drops of triethylamine were added. This step was important to deprotonate the carboxylic acid group and prevent unnecessary protonation of formamide. A light green fine crystalline precipitate formed, which was filtered under vacuum through a Büchner funnel, washed with ethanol, and dried. The precipitate was also washed several times with cold methanol, and the absence of chloride ions in the coordination compound was confirmed by testing with 0.1 M

AgNO₃ solution. The mass of the synthesized complex compound was measured, and the reaction yield was calculated. The yield (η) was found to be 67% [25].

Reaction equation:

II. The coordination compound **Co(ket)₂(CH₃CONH₂)₂(H₂O)₂** was also synthesized by the above-mentioned method, and the reaction equation can be expressed as follows.

Reaction equation:

The yield (η) was found to be 68%.

III. The coordination compound **[Co(Ket)₂(C₆H₆N₂O)₂(H₂O)₂]** was also synthesized by the above-mentioned method, and the reaction equation can be expressed as follows.

The yield (η) was found to be 72%.

“Nicotinamide (nia) > Acetamide (acm) > Formamide (fm)”. In this sequence, the activity of the amides decreases. Nicotinamide is the strongest amide in the series, and the complex formed with it is the most stable and was obtained with the highest yield. All the synthesized complexes were obtained in colored forms: the nicotinamide complex appeared as blue-violet precipitates, the acetamide complex as brown precipitates, and the formamide complex as light-green precipitates. The composition of the synthesized coordination compounds was determined by elemental analysis, and the following results were obtained [26]. The metal content in the synthesized complexes was determined using a novAA 300 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena AG, Germany) [27], while the elemental composition was analyzed with a EuroEA3000 CHNS-O Analyzer (Eurovector S.p.A., Milan, Italy) [28].

Table 1

Elemental analysis results of cobalt–ketorolac–amide coordination compounds

No	Coordination compound formula	Molecular formula:	Chemical elements	Theoretical %	Experimental %
1	[Co(Ket) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₈ Co M=603.53 g/mol	C	59,7	59,35
			H	4,69	4,82
			N	4,64	4,51
			O	21,20	-
2	[Co(Ket) ₂ (HCONH ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] yoki [Co(Ket) ₂ (fm) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	C ₃₂ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Co M=693.63 g/mol	C	55,41	55,12
			H	4,95	5,11
			N	8,08	7,89
			O	23,06	-
3	[Co(Ket) ₂ (CH ₃ CONH ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] yoki [Co(Ket) ₂ (acm) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	C ₃₄ H ₃₈ N ₄ O ₁₀ Co M=721.69 g/mol	C	56,58	56,20
			H	5,32	5,45
			N	7,77	7,62
			O	22,17	-
			C	59,36	58,95

4	[Co(Ket) ₂ (C ₆ H ₆ N ₂ O) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] yoki [Co(Ket) ₂ (nia) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	C ₄₂ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₁₀ C o M=849.83 g/mol	H	4,99	5,18
	N		9,89	9,65	
	O		18,87	-	
	Co		6,93	6,75	

Analysis and results. Since the differences between the spectra of the initial components and those of the complexes provide information about new interactions and bond formations, IR spectroscopy data were used to analyze the structures of the obtained complexes. The IR absorption spectra were recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a “SHIMADZU” IRAffinity-1S spectrometer [29].

Figure 1. IR spectrum of the [Co(Ket)₂(fm)₂(H₂O)₂] complex compound

Figure 2. IR spectrum of the [Co(Ket)₂(acm)₂(H₂O)₂] complex compound

Figure 3. IR spectrum of the $[Co(Ket)_2(nia)_2(H_2O)_2]$ complex compound

The IR spectra of ketorolac, cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate, and the complex compound synthesized from these two components were analyzed. In the spectrum of ketorolac, characteristic absorption bands of C=O stretching vibrations were observed at 1720 and 1705 cm⁻¹ [30], corresponding to the carbonyl group of the carboxylic moiety. Additionally, O–H stretching vibrations of the carboxyl group appeared in the range of 2729–2749 cm⁻¹. In the spectrum of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate, vibrational modes of water molecules and the amino group were recorded: O–H stretching at 3369 and 3560 cm⁻¹, and asymmetric and symmetric N–H₂ stretching at 3311 and 3225 cm⁻¹, respectively. Low-frequency vibrations attributed to Co–O bonds were also observed in the range of 535–565 cm⁻¹.

In the spectrum of the complex synthesized from ketorolac and cobalt(II) nitrate, the C=O stretching bands of ketorolac were shifted from 1732 to 1739 cm⁻¹ and from 1693 to 1683 cm⁻¹, indicating coordination of the C=O group with the cobalt ion. Furthermore, the disappearance of the broad O–H stretching bands suggests deprotonation of the carboxyl group upon complex formation with Co(II). New absorption bands in the 530–570 cm⁻¹ region confirm the formation of Co–O bonds.

Based on these IR spectral analyses, it is evident that a coordination complex is formed between ketorolac and cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate. The ketorolac molecule coordinates to the Co(II) ion via its carboxyl group. The shift of the C=O stretching vibrations, disappearance of O–H bands, and the appearance of new Co–O vibrations serve as direct evidence of complex formation (Figures 1–3).

The antibacterial properties of ketorolac and the metal–complex compounds synthesized on its basis were studied *in vitro* under laboratory conditions against strains from the microorganism collection of the Institute of Microbiology, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan: *Bacillus subtilis*-5, *Escherichia coli*-221, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*-225, *Staphylococcus aureus*-91, and *Candida albicans*-247 [31]. The effects of the ligand (HL) and the complex compounds on non-spore-forming test strains were determined during the exponential growth phase (after 36–42 hours), while their effects on spore-forming test strains were assessed during the sporulation stage (after 48–72 hours). Antibacterial activity was evaluated on the 3rd–5th day of incubation, based

on the diameter of the sterile zones formed in Petri dishes where the test strains were inoculated and the samples were applied (Egorov, 1995; Egorov, 2003). To minimize experimental error, all experiments were repeated three times.

The antibacterial activities of the chemical compounds were studied in comparison with the ligand, including HL and its complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, and $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (each at 0.03 mmol), which showed varying degrees of activity (Table 2). The results revealed that the samples were capable of inhibiting, to some extent, the growth and development of opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms (inhibition zones of 9–20 mm). Among the tested samples, the complex compounds demonstrated the highest bactericidal activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, with a lysis zone of 25 mm.

Figure 4. Antimicrobial activity of ketorolac (HL) and its synthesized complex compounds against microorganisms (3–5 days).

All the test microorganisms exhibited significantly higher activity compared to free ketorolac and cobalt chloride. This confirms the main advantage of chelation: the lipophilicity of the complex increases, which facilitates its easier penetration through the bacterial cell membrane (Figure 4). All mixed-ligand complexes demonstrated higher activity than the parent complex, indicating the potential for further enhancement of their biological activity.

Table 2

Inhibition zone diameters (mm) for different bacteria

№	Compound	abbreviation	Staphylococcus aureus	Bacillus subtilis	Escherichia coli	Pseudomonas aeruginosa
1	Ketorolac	KetH	8	7	6	5
2	Formamide	fm	7	6	5	4
3	Acetamide	acm	8	7	6	5
4	Nicotinamide	nia	9	8	7	6
5	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	I	12	11	10	9
6	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	II	14	13	11	10
7	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	III	16	15	13	11
8	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	IV	19	18	15	13
9	Ampicillin (Standard)	-	25	24	22	20
10	DMSO (Control)	-	0	0	0	0

All complexes exhibited slightly lower activity against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*) compared to Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*). This is a common phenomenon, since the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria provides an additional protective barrier, resisting the penetration of substances. The study of the antibacterial activity of the investigated complexes showed that, compared to the free ligand, the cobalt-containing

complex displayed higher activity. Moreover, the complexes containing amides demonstrated stronger activity against all tested strains, with inhibition zone diameters ranging approximately from 9 to 20 mm. Thus, all the synthesized complexes were able to suppress the growth and development of microorganisms more effectively than the initial ligand and corresponding salts.

Conclusion. New mixed-ligand complexes – $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, and $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ – were successfully synthesized in a reproducible manner using ketorolac tromethamine, the corresponding cobalt(II) salt, and various amides in an aqueous–methanol medium. Shifts observed in the IR spectra confirmed that ketorolac coordinates to the cobalt(II) ion via its carboxylate group in a bidentate mode, while the amides act as monodentate ligands through either oxygen (fm, acm) or nitrogen (nia) donor atoms. All synthesized cobalt(II) complexes exhibited higher antibacterial activity compared to the free ligands (ketorolac and amides) and even the simple $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex. This clearly demonstrates the significant role of complex formation in enhancing antibiotic activity. Among the mixed-ligand complexes, antibacterial efficacy was found to depend on the nature and coordinating ability of the amide ligand, following the trend:

This order is attributed to the strong N-donor properties of nicotinamide, which enhances both the stability of the complex and its ability to penetrate bacterial cell membranes. In conclusion, an efficient synthetic approach for cobalt(II) mixed-ligand complexes based on ketorolac was developed, and their antibacterial properties, particularly in the case of the nicotinamide complex, were clearly demonstrated. These complexes represent promising candidates for further evaluation, including toxicological and in vivo studies, as potential new and effective antibacterial agents.

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